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HEAVENS

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Abstract

Let's turn to Heavens. The knowledges that we have today and, the most important, the conclusions that we have drawn from them and pass them off as truth, are well known to everyone.

The main tool that gives astronomers information about "endless" space of the Universe and what is in – it's a telescope. As more powerful telescope we have as farther we see. And, accordingly, if we don't see the body (star) in a smaller telescope and see in a larger one, then this body (star) is further away.

The Quran says that God made Heavens out of seven sky's and put the stars on the first from us. Therefore, it's logically to assume that in telescopes we see the "bottom" of this first sky, and the more powerful the telescope the more detailed it shows "this sole". This is my assumption.

Keywords: heavens, light, origin, space, telescope, astronomers, universe, Hubble, probes, stars.

"He is The One who created everything on the Earth for us, then He turned to the Heavens and built it from the seven skys. He knows everything!"

Let's turn to Heavens too. The knowledges that we have today and, the most important, the conclusions that we have drawn from them and pass them off as truth, are well known to everyone. Let's analyze where we got and get any knowledges about structure and size of the Universe?

The main tool that gives astronomers information about "endless" space of the Universe and what is in – it's a telescope. Increasing the resolution of the telescope we "looking deep into the Universe." We think so.

Lets answer to the question about difference between a microscope and a telescope[1]. They differ in two things - in size and in tasks. But their principle of action is the same - to increase and approximate. When we look through a microscope and explore what is in focus, we understand that we are considering the detailed structure of the body we are studying. And as

more magnifying microscope we take as smaller "details" of the body we can see.

With a telescope we have completely different idea. As more powerful telescope we have as farther we see. And, accordingly, if we don't see the body (star) in a smaller telescope and see in a larger one, then this body (star) is further away.

The Quran [2] says that God made Heavens out of seven sky's and put the stars on the first from us.

Therefore, it's logically to assume that in telescopes we see the "bottom" of this first sky, and the more powerful the telescope the more detailed it shows "this sole". This is an assumption, what evidence is available. Let's try to analyze it.

1. Hubble telescope [3]. This telescope was built to "look into the past". At the time of its creation (according to scientists) size and age of the universe was 7-10 billion years. Hubble had to look further than these 10 billion years and show what happened in the Universe immediately after the Big Bang. With Hubble we saw the same stars (stellar systems) that we saw and explored before. Therefore, this telescope increased the age of the Universe to 13-15 billion years. To look further, it is necessary to build more powerful telescope - scientists think so. I'm sure the next telescope will show what happened before the Big Bang. And the next one even more. And so it will be to infinity.

2. The American space probes Pioneer 10 and Pioneer 11 were launched in 1972 and 1973. By now, they should have already left the solar system. However, both - first and second - for unknown reasons changed their trajectory, as if an unknown force didn't let them out of the system. Pioneer 10 has already deviated by four hundred thousand kilometers from the calculated trajectory. Pioneer 11 exactly follows the path of its predecessor. There are many versions: the influence of the solar wind, fuel leakage, programming

errors. But all of them aren't very convincing cause both ships launched with interval on 1 year behave in the same way.

So there are two facts which approves that we can see sole of the first sky from us in telescopes, and probes move along the sole of this first sky [4].

3. It's a fact that the Universe have dark (hidden) material which cannot be spotted: no one known method of research isn't work. I guess "dark material" is what with the first sky was create. As the Prophet Muhammad said, the material of this sky consists iron mainly.

These facts based on the modern knowledges of science. Further assumptions will be based on knowledges from the Quran and from one very interesting fact from history.

What we know from the Quran:

Surah 2, 27 (29). He is The One who created everything on the Earth for us,

then He turned to the Heavens and built it from the seven skys. He knows everything!

Surah 3, 9. Allah is rich, above the worlds!

Surah 24, 35 (35). Allah is the light of Heaven and earth.

Surah 37, 6 (6). We've butified the nearest sky with stars.

God is light. That's why the light we see comes from God. We know that the Moon shines by reflected light from the Sun. As known, the Sun shines from the center, not from the edge, so I think that the Sun also shines with the light reflected from God.

"The Sun is the 'mirror' into which God looks". From the conversation of the Prophet Moses with God we know that nothing and no one can look at God. If that happen – it or he/she suffer. It turns out that the Sun is the only object in our world that can withstand the "sight" of God.

Let's go next. There is an interesting fact in history that will help us to think about what kind of light can be in Heaven. This fact suggests that in the 12th century a girl and a boy with green skin appeared in England. They went down in history as the "green children of Woolpit" [7]. Before they came to England they lived in a country of green people where the sun never rises, and far from their land a brightly land (island) was visible. The children entered a cave on their planet and exited from mine in England.

God is above everything, and above the seven skys which he created. He is light. As you know, light is scattered into seven colors (red, orange, yellow, green, blue, dark blue, violet). I guess the light from God, passing through each sky, loses one of its colors. Passing through the first sky it loses red, through the second - orange, etc. After the seventh heaven it "extinguishes" completely. In the fourth heaven there is a constant

green light and people with green skin. Another interesting fact that the "green" girl told us: "... a brightly land is visible in the distance, separated from their country by a wide river." There is no sun but how there can be an illuminated earth? I think this "illuminated earth" is one of the "holes" where the light from God comes through and which we see as stars.

Most likely this multiple source of light from all "stars" creates radiance hitting the Sun and reflecting from it. It is quite possible [5] that light, passing through the "air" layers of the Sun (hydrogen, helium, etc.), is reflected from its liquid layer and amplified by multiple reflections from the air and liquid layers with the same way as light is amplified in gas laser installations. Perhaps this "laser amplification" creates a millionth temperature of the solar corona [6].

By creation of skys the Sun shone according to the Bible [10] only on the third day. Those skys and holes in them were necessary in order to let light through and focus it on the Sun.

Here are my guesses. What proofs can there be? We have proofs in photographs taken by the Hubble telescope [8].

If you look at these photos you can see there almost all colors of all skys. And the most common color is purple. It proves the light that is scattered by the gas contained in the first sky from us and in seventh from God. Why do we see red gas in the first sky, you ask? Because there are too big holes in Heaven that reach up to the seventh sky from us.

Sakhipov D.M. 2008. Russia, Nizhnevartovsk, Ufa.

This article was written by me in 2008 and has not been published anywhere. Too big gulf lies between modern knowledges and my assumptions. But, time is going and new facts appearing. These facts now able to confirm my rightness or refute it. What's new for today?

1. The James Webb telescope is launched. It "pushes" the borders of our Universe even further. It was the first show me what the sole of the first sky from us looks like. (Photo 2 [13]). What can we see? A star looking like a "screwed light bulb" and rings framing it. This is exactly a hole in the sky, and light breaks through and Ring Mountains that were created for the light which coming out of the hole couldn't illuminate the bottom of the sky. There are many of them, because if the nearest sky and the next after will be destroyed, the remaining skies will keep the bottom black. We can see an example of such destruction in Photo 3 (zoomed part of Photo 2) from the bottom right. It can be seen that the ring closest to the "star" and, possibly, others below and to the right are destroyed, and the greatest amount of light is scattered.

Photo 2. Webb Telescope October 13, 2022

Photo 3. Center zoom of Photo 2

2. After the Photo 2 of the Webb telescope, literally by 10 days later, the Hubble telescope shoots two "stars" with ring mountains around them [11].

Photo 4. Hubble telescope October 23, 2022

Photo 5. A bright star to the right of the center of Photo 4.

Photo 6. A small star from the top right of the center of Photo 4.

3. Sura 41, verse 11. "Then He turned to the Heaven, which was smoke". This verse tells us that before creation "Heaven" was "smoke", or gas (most likely of different composition). From various gases God created the skys. What remains of these gases we see in the form of "Pillars of Creation", "Galaxies", etc

[8]. Due to the fact that they are illuminated by the "stars - holes" behind them, we see these remains of gases. "Galaxies" have a spiral shapes because they are remains of gases from which the ring mountains were created.

As known, a gas with a certain composition, when light is passed through it, turns into a certain color. Oxygen to blue, helium to yellow, and so on. For getting different colors in the photographs of the Hubble and Webb telescopes holes in the sky are not needed, what about I wrote earlier. It's enough that the gases that remained after creation the sole of sky are highlighted.

4. What can destroy a ring mountain? Answer: comets. I always wondered: "Why haven't comets disappeared over "billions" of years, constantly losing their substances, approaching the Sun and moving away from it?". The clue is that they constantly replenish them (substances), rolling on the sole and sticking it like a snowball.

I wrote about space probes earlier. "Pioneers" behaved strangely. Now nothing is written about them, but the Voyager probes have woken up, and one of them is already returning back, apparently having "pushed off" from the sole of the first sky [12].

5. Another fact that has already been established: the spectral analysis of dark matter has been determined. It consists of iron, manganese, hydrocarbon, chromium. Even the Prophet Muhammad said that the first sky mainly consists of iron. Most likely, the spectral analysis tells us that the sole of the first sky imainly composed of austenitic (manganese)-alloying (chromium) steel (iron + carbon) [9].

Sakhipov D.M. July 20, 2023. Russia, Nizhnevartovsk, Ufa.

To be continued...

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